

INTERNATIONAL NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS AND PROTECTION OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS

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Summary. *In the article, the issues of international non-governmental organizations and the protection of children's rights are extensively analyzed based on the existing diversity of opinions in the legal literature and international practice. It is noted that international non-governmental organizations carry out important activities in the protection of human rights, including children's rights. At this time, it is necessary to mention a number of main activities of international non-governmental organizations: protection of children's rights during military conflicts; protection of the rights of orphans and children deprived of parental care; development of juvenile justice; development of children's educational and other cultural rights; development of children's rights for a better life; and so on. The main characteristic of the modern era is the further expansion of these areas of activity.*

At the end of the article, it is concluded that a number of important methods are used by international non-governmental organizations for activities in these directions: participation in the process of preparing important international agreements (convention, declaration, agreement, pact, protocol, etc.) in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of preparing international reports in separate fields; participation in the process of collecting and transferring information on violations of human rights, including children's rights, to international organizations in individual states; participation in the process of supporting international cooperation efforts of states; participation in the process of developing various types of joint activities with the states to support the individual rights of children; participation in the process of cooperation with international intergovernmental organizations in the protection of children's rights; participation in the process of further development of the national legislation of the states in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of preparation and implementation of universal and regional international programs covering individual regions in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of forming new international control mechanisms for ensuring children's rights; participation in the process of formation of new international non-governmental organizations in the field of children's rights; improvement of national mechanisms in the field of children's rights, including participation in the process of further increasing the activity of national non-governmental organizations; and etc.

Keywords. *children's rights, human rights, international non-governmental organizations, military conflicts, international relations, international organizations, human rights violations.*

In recent years, there has been a trend related to the creation of a large number of international non-governmental organizations in almost all countries of the world. Thus, researchers of international non-governmental organizations note that they observe unusual activity in the creation of private, commercial organizations, voluntary organizations, associations, and foundations [5, p.143-150; 6, p.10-13]. Modern international relations are characterized by the increasing

number of international non-governmental organizations, the expansion of their role and importance in the modern world, international cooperation, and the active determination of the place and legal status of these types of organizations in international law. The creation and activity of non-governmental organizations have become an object of research in legal literature for a long time. This type of research is aimed at helping to solve global problems such as the nature of international non-governmental organizations, conditions for their creation, international legal status, international security, protection of human rights, protection of the environment, etc. to states and international intergovernmental organizations.

Currently, more and more states and the world community as a whole are beginning to understand that it is necessary to look for new, mainly non-traditional approaches to solving the problems of people's better and more prosperous life, to create and reorganize new mechanisms to coordinate the efforts of states in this direction. . One of the opportunities that really exists, but is not used at the global level, is the recognition by states of the partnership role of their societies, represented by numerous non-governmental organizations whose activities in the international arena do not in any way threaten the democratic regime. Moreover, the activities of these types of organizations strengthen the potential of their state, and at the same time increase their international reputation.

According to experts conducting research in this direction in the scientific literature, international non-governmental organizations act as the main form of civil society and representation in the modern world, shape the public interests of different layers of the population of the countries of the world during their activities, participate in the development and preparation of international norms and international court proceedings by using their own means and methods, monitor compliance with the principles and norms of international law, and in some cases perform an independent, impartial function in resolving legal disputes at the request of interested states [11, p. 28-34].

The increase in the number of international non-governmental organizations and their growing influence in the international world is related to a number of factors. Among these factors, the following should be emphasized: the emergence of new global problems for the solution of which the capabilities of states and international organizations are no longer sufficient; the diversity of relations between nations that need new international institutions to realize themselves; the strengthening of democratic processes in the field of internal and international relations of states, as a manifestation of this, the desire to make society more open and transparent; transformation in the field of national

interests of states; initiatives to increase control over decision-making processes in matters affecting the vital interests of individuals worldwide; expansion of cross-border communication and activity opportunities of the public of different countries, as well as expansion of technological progress opportunities; increase in human rights violations in various areas, including children's rights; threats to peace and international security; the need to increase the fight against international crime; etc.

In this regard, according to a number of authors, humanity has entered such a stage of development of international relations that states have already begun to objectively distance themselves from the idea of being the only subjects of international relations [8, p. 36-46]. Although international non-governmental organizations act as serious international players, their effective influence and opportunities in international relations are often not adequately reflected in international law.

The relevance and timeliness of the scientific analysis of the activity of international non-governmental organizations is related to the fact that, despite previous scientific research, there is currently no consensus on the fact of the active activity of international non-governmental organizations in the world. Determining the legal status of international non-governmental organizations is not sufficiently connected with objective reality, their potential in solving international problems and development prospects are not fully determined. Currently, there are no norms in international law that would officially recognize the international legal status of international non-governmental organizations, on the other hand, there are no norms denying the ability of international non-governmental organizations to be subjects of international law and international relations.

It is noted in the legal literature that international non-governmental organizations operate mainly in two directions: informal formulation and promotion of new international legal norms as an initial response to the urgent demand of the world community; putting pressure on governments in various forms so that states fulfill their obligations under international law. As a whole, the activity of international non-governmental organizations in the field of human rights is conventionally expressed in a number of areas in the legal literature: mobilizing public opinion to reveal the violation of human rights and seriously criticize that situation; providing direct legal assistance to victims of human rights violations by international non-governmental organizations; helping to adopt new norms in the field of human rights in international organizations; provision of legal and technical assistance, dissemination of knowledge about human rights [1, p. 246-247].

Thus, based on the ideas expressed in local and foreign legal literature, the provisions mentioned in international documents, as well as a number of specific features put forward, an international non-governmental organization - created in accordance with national legislation to achieve the development goals and tasks of civil society and international relations, can be defined as a self-organizing association of public representatives of different states operating in the territory of two or more states, having consultative status, in accordance with the UN Charter and generally recognized principles of international law. The activities of international non-governmental organizations are diverse and this sphere has expanded even more. In general, in the legal literature, non-governmental organizations are sometimes defined as organizations that prevent the excessive concentration of power and authority, draw the attention of governments to human rights issues such as the status of women, children's rights, the rights and opportunities of minorities, and perform certain functions.

One of such functions and the most important one is related to the activity of non-governmental structures in the field of protection of human rights and observance of these rights. In general, international non-governmental organizations have the opportunity to participate in the development of new standards (conventions) in the field of human rights protection. Initiatives or even ready-made projects from non-governmental organizations often enter international integration structures, and their representatives also actively participate in the work on new international cooperation tools in the field of human rights protection. Human rights non-governmental organizations press governments to draw the authorities' attention to violations and prompt immediate resolution of a specific human rights problem. At the national level, it is non-governmental organizations that support the recommendations and decisions of intergovernmental organizations, and at the same time expand their influence by creating new structures.

Transnational networks in the field of human rights created under the auspices of international non-governmental organizations are one of the forms of collective assistance in the observance of human rights as generally accepted norms in the modern world. The historical experience of the activity of such international networks, which were established in the middle of the 19th century in North American and European countries and mainly demanded the protection of children's rights, anti-slavery, and women's suffrage rights, proved the necessity of action in this direction in the UN system in the middle of the 20th century [3, p. 22]. A new era of international human rights networks began with the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 and continued to develop over the following decades when a broad structure of international institutions for the protection of human rights began to be created.

In parallel, new international non-governmental organizations began to emerge in this direction. In particular, organizations such as the International Amnesty Organization (Amnesty International), which was established in 1961, formed the main component of the international movement for the protection of human rights [7, p. 34-35]. In modern times, Amnesty International is recognized as the largest international non-governmental organization in the field of human rights protection. The organization calls for the release of prisoners of conscience around the world, calls for the unconditional abolition of the death penalty, fights against all forms of discrimination, defends the right of expression for everyone, and protects sexual and reproductive rights, including the rights of refugees and migrants. In 1964, Amnesty International received the status of advisor to the UN, then the Council of Europe and UNESCO. Since then, Amnesty International has started providing information on the number of political prisoners in certain countries to the UN Human Rights Committee. Since the 2000s, Amnesty International has been raising global issues around the world. Its field of activity includes the protection of economic, social, and cultural human rights [10, p. 78]. At the beginning of the 21st century, Amnesty International focused its activities on several main areas: the struggle for the abolition of the death penalty; fighting to end violence against women; protecting the rights of people living below the poverty line; protecting the rights of refugees and migrants; arms trade control; ending torture and inhumane treatment of prisoners in the fight against terrorism; protection of children's rights [9, p. 149]. Currently headquartered in London, the Organization has more than 70 national chapters, more than 7,500 affiliated local groups, and 7 million members monitoring human rights violations in more than 150 countries.

High financial support enables Amnesty International to carry out its campaigns effectively. The main method of its activity is to attract the attention of the public to the facts of human rights violations and to put pressure on the competent authorities of the respective country through appeals (letters, telegrams, faxes, postcards, e-mails, and text messages). Amnesty International regularly publishes reports and periodicals on human rights issues, which highlight human rights violations in individual countries.

As for the protection of children during military conflicts, it should be noted that Amnesty International does not take sides during military conflicts and accuses children's rights violations in the same way. Amnesty International opposes human rights abuses by both government forces and military units, defends the rights of children in conflict zones, and helps restore the rights of refugee and internally displaced children.

Human Rights Watch (HRW) is an international human rights non-governmental organization headquartered in New York. It operates in more than 70

countries of the world. The organization does not receive financial assistance from government agencies and is supported by private donations. Currently, the organization operates in the following areas: prevention of discrimination; protection of political freedoms; investigating and publishing human rights violations; investigating genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity; preventing the proliferation and use of anti-personnel mines; fight against child exploitation and recruitment of child soldiers; helping orphaned children; ending torture, combating extrajudicial death sentences; organizing court cases against human rights violators; fight against human trafficking and sexual slavery; protection of the rights of sexual minorities; protection of civilians during military operations.

One of the leading organizations in this field is the Pro Bono Institute (PBI). It is a non-profit organization whose mission is to research and identify new approaches to providing legal services to the poor, disadvantaged, and other individuals or groups who cannot afford legal aid. The Pro Bono Institute mainly operates in the following areas: attracting experts to the provision of pro bono legal assistance; studying the laws governing the provision of pro bono legal assistance and publishing special periodicals on this topic; allocating resources in the most efficient way to increase work in this field by assisting large law firms and legal corporations providing pro bono legal assistance.

The American Bar Association (ABA) is one of the organizations providing free legal assistance, which has a special place in the international legal system. It is a legal association whose main purpose is to develop an institution of free legal aid. However, this direction is part of its activity. The preparation of reports in the field of human rights is one of the main areas here.

The International Bar Association (IBA) is one of the prestigious organizations whose main activity is the provision of legal services free of charge. This organization consists of more than 30,000 lawyers and 195 legal associations and communities from more than 180 countries around the world.

One of the most important functions of international non-governmental organizations is information provision. The dissemination of information about human rights and delivery of information about their violation is of particular importance in this context.

One of the largest international organizations in the field of human rights, the Robert F. Kennedy Human Rights Organization (Robert F. Kennedy Human Rights - RFK) has developed a special project called "Speak truth to Power" [2, p. 89]. The range of issues the organization deals with is quite wide: from slavery and the fight for the environment to religious self-determination and political participation.

One of the international non-governmental organizations operating in this field is the International Committee of the Red Cross. The organization, being a

humanitarian organization that carries out its activities all over the world based on the principle of neutrality and impartiality, provides assistance to the victims of military conflicts and internal conflicts and defends the victims of those conflicts. The issue of children's involvement in military service has always been a serious concern of the Committee. The prevention of such incidents is the most important priority for the organization. This is done through the development of precise legal standards and the implementation of activities on the ground.

As a humanitarian organization, the International Committee of the Red Cross, in accordance with its traditions and mandate, adopts legal norms on the protection of children in military conflicts and implements activities for their protection in various directions. The initiative of the committee often allows to ensure the legal protection of children in the course of military conflicts and at the same time, it is considered an effective tool in cases where the mechanism of application of international legal norms does not produce effective results.

The Committee continues to support relations with representatives of the government and military units, with warnings about their obligations and the ban on the recruitment of children into military service. Thus, it succeeds in achieving the demobilization of many children. After demobilization, the committee does everything possible to reunite these children with their parents and families. If the security situation allows the reunification of parents and children and serves the interests of this child, the Committee mobilizes all its possibilities to realize this process. The International Committee of the Red Cross has adopted many international legal documents aimed at protecting the rights of children in military conflicts, specifically, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict, etc. closely participated in the development of documents and acted as the main expert. During the implementation of its activities, the committee cooperates closely with UNICEF [4, p. 21-23].

Among the influential international non-governmental organizations involved in the protection of children's rights related to military conflicts, Human Rights Watch occupies an important place. This international non-governmental organization, which was established in 1978 and monitors, investigates and documents human rights violations, operates in more than 70 countries of the world. The issues raised in the organization's reports cover spheres such as social and gender discrimination, torture, use of children in wars, political corruption, abuses in the criminal justice system, etc. The organization strives to end violations of children's rights, including executions, torture, prevention of the involvement of minors in military conflicts, etc. as reflected in the reports of the organization. The organization pays special attention to the facts of torture against children, and such an approach is defined that regardless of the parties

to the military conflict if children's rights are violated in that conflict, all parties to the conflict should consider the solution of this problem as the first priority.

In addition, the Women's World Summit Foundation, an international non-governmental organization, publishes a biennial global newsletter entitled "Empowering Women and Children" in four languages (English, French, Spanish and Russian), thereby ensures the wide dissemination of its reports on work with the UN. In addition, in 1996, the Foundation established the World Fund for the Dignity of Children in order to end the sexual exploitation of children and to call on nations to eliminate such practices. This institution played a fundamental role in attracting new members by emphasizing the right of children to dignity, helping public organizations to understand it, and using leaflets and publications about this serious social deficiency [1, p. 248].

As can be seen, international non-governmental organizations carry out important activities in the protection of human rights, including children's rights. Therefore, it is necessary to mention a number of main activities of international non-governmental organizations: protection of children's rights during military conflicts; protection of the rights of orphans and children deprived of parental care; development of juvenile justice; development of children's educational and other cultural rights; development of children's rights for a better life, etc. The main characteristic of the modern era is the further expansion of these areas of activity.

A number of important methods are used by international non-governmental organizations for activities in these directions: participation in the process of preparing important international agreements (convention, declaration, agreement, pact, protocol, etc.) in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of preparing international reports in separate fields; participation in the process of collecting and transferring information on violations of human rights, including children's rights, to international organizations in individual states; participation in the process of supporting international cooperation efforts of states; participation in the process of developing various types of joint activities with the states to support the individual rights of children; participation in the process of cooperation with international intergovernmental organizations in the protection of children's rights; participation in the process of further development of the national legislation of the states in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of preparation and implementation of universal and regional international programs covering individual regions in the field of children's rights; participation in the process of forming new international control mechanisms for ensuring children's rights; participation in the process of formation of new international non-governmental organizations in the field of children's rights; improvement of national mechanisms in the field of children's rights, including participation in the process of further increasing the activity of national non-governmental organizations, etc.

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